

ONLINE PAYMENT METHODS AND ITS IMPACT ON CUSTOMER TRUST

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INTRODUCTION:

In recent years, the rapid growth of online payments has revolutionized how consumers interact with businesses. As online shopping and digital transactions have become integral parts of everyday life, the methods by which consumers pay for goods and services online have evolved significantly. The emergence of a variety of online payment methods, ranging from traditional credit and debit cards to newer, innovative solutions such as digital wallets, cryptocurrencies, and buy-now-pay-later services, has made it easier and more convenient for consumers to complete transactions from anywhere in the world. However, maintaining client trust is a challenge that comes with the ease of online payments. The dependability and security of online payment systems have been under scrutiny due to worries about fraud, privacy, and security. When deciding whether or not customers are prepared to accept new payment methods or make transactions online, trust is a critical consideration. Therefore, in an increasingly competitive and digital economy, it is critical for firms looking to establish and preserve good client connections to comprehend how various payment methods affect consumer trust. The purpose of this study is to investigate the connection between consumer trust and online payment options. This study attempts to clarify how the choice of payment method can affect consumer behaviour and trust in digital transactions by looking at elements including perceived security of various payment systems, usability, and the part user experience plays in forming customer confidence.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To investigate how demographic characteristics, affect consumers' confidence in online payment methods.
- To determine the elements that affect consumers' confidence in online payment methods.
- To assess the degree of trust that consumers have in various online payment methods.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data collection method: The study used both primary data and Secondary data. Primary data is collected from respondents through questionnaires using Google forms. Secondary data were

collected through websites, journals and newspapers. Sample Size was 100 respondents from Coimbatore City. The tools used for the data analysis is simple percentage.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Cheung, C. M. K., & Lee, M. K. O. (2006)

Consumer Trust in Online Shopping

This study examines the factors that contribute to consumer trust in online shopping, including security, privacy, and reliability of online payment systems. It provides a broad conceptualization of trust within the e-commerce environment. The research emphasizes that trust in online payment systems (such as credit card security, encryption, and data protection) is a fundamental determinant of consumer trust in online shopping environments. Consumers are more likely to trust and complete purchases when they feel confident in the security of their payment options.

Punj, G. (2011)

Demographic characteristics and consumption value has a great impact on online purchase behaviour.

The study reveals that saving time and saving money is most valuable belief of consumer that has the impact on online purchase behaviour, that helps the consumers for finding the products as per the need and demand of the consumer. Findings of research results show that saving money and saving time impacts the online consumer. These beliefs have a modest effect of demographic characteristics like age, gender income, education and by consumption value.

Sharma and Mehta (2014)

Online purchase behaviour of Indian shopper

This study focuses on online buying behaviour of India. This research focused on different factors 10 analysis and interpretation the result it shows that online shopping stores have a more significant impact on Indian consumer. Ease and comfort are important factors that were affect when consumer visiting the virtual store. This study reveals that there is the massive scope of web store in various areas and in almost all segment. The majority of internet users are youngsters in India.

Md Anower Hossain (2024)

Impact of online payment systems on customer trust and loyalty in e-commerce analysing security and convenience

This study systematically reviews the impact of online payment systems on customer trust and loyalty in e-commerce, adhering to PRISMA guidelines. The findings highlight the critical importance of security, convenience, and transparency in shaping customer perceptions and behaviours.

Analysis & Intrepretation

TABLE 1 : OFTEN DO YOU SHOP ONLINE

SOURCES	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	%
Daily	14	14%
Weekly	21	21%
Monthly	40	40%
Rarely	25	25%
Total	100	100%

INTERPRETATION:

The table shows that, 14% are daily shoppers, 21% are weekly shoppers, 40% are monthly shoppers and 25% are rarely shoppers.

TABLE 2 : ONLINE PAYMENT METHOD YOU PREFER

SOURCE	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	%
Credit/Debit Card	19	19%
Digital wallets	15	15%
Net banking	21	21%
UPI	45	45%
Total	100	100%

INTERPRETATION:

The table inferred that, 19% are Credit/Debit Card users, 15% are Digital wallet users, 21% are Net banking users and 45% are UPI users.

TABLE 3 : FACTORS INFLUENCING ONLINE PAYMENT METHOD

FACTORS	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	%
Security	29	29%
Ease of Use	34	34%
Convenience	24	24%
Trust	13	13%
Total	100	100%

INTERPRETAION:

The above table shows that, 29% of respondents agree that online payment method is security, 34% of agree that Ease of Use, 4% of agree that more Convenience and 13% of respondents Trust the online payment method.

TABLE 4 : SECURE FEEL OVER ONLINE PAYMENT METHOD

STATEMENT	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	%
Very Secure	19	19%
Secure	34	34%
Neutral	37	37%
Somewhat insecure	10	10%
Very insecure	0	0
Total	100	100%

INTERPRETATION:

In this study, 19% respondents feel Very secure, 34% respondents feel Secure. 37% respondents feel Neutral and 10% respondents feel Somewhat secure.

TABLE 5 : FRAUD THAT IMPACT YOUR TRUST

STATEMENT	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	%
No impact	35	35%
Slightly reduced trust	27	27%
Significantly reduced trust	25	25%
Completely stopped using online payment	13	13%
Total	100	100%

INTERPRETATION:

This table shows that, 35% thinks No impact, 27% thinks Slightly reduced trust, 25% thinks Significantly reduced trust and 13% Completely stopped using online payment.

TABLE 6 : IMPROVEMENT TO SEE IN ONLINE PAYMENT SECURITY

SOURCE	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	%
Strong Biometric Authentication	49	49%
Multi Factor Authentication	40	40%
Encrypted Digital Wallets	11	11%
Total	100	100%

INTERPRETATION:

The table shows that, 49% of respondents said Strong Biometric Authentication, 40% said Multi Factor Authentication and 11% said Multi Factor Authentication while using online payment.

TABLE 7 : PAYMENT FAILURES WHILE MAKING ONLINE TRANSACTIONS

SOURCE	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	%
Always	28	28%
Sometimes	34	34%
Rarely	30	30%
Never	8	8%
Total	100	100%

INTERPRETATION:

The table shows that, 28% respondents said that Always payment failures while doing online payment, 34% said Sometimes, 30% said Rarely and 8% said Never facing payment failures while making online transaction.

TABLE 8 : IF PAYMENT FAILS DURING AN ONLINE TRANSACTIONS

STATEMENT	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	%
Try a different payment method	50	50%
Contact Customer Support	25	25%
Abandon the purchase	15	15%
Other	10	10%
Total	100	100

INTERPRETATION:

The table shows that, 50% said Try a different payment method, 25% said Contact Customer Support, 15% said Contact Customer Support and 10% said Other reasons.

TABLE 9 : LEVEL OF SATISFACTION

SOURCE	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	%
Very Satisfied	32	32%
Satisfied	34	34%
Neutral	27	27%
Dissatisfied	2	2%
Very dissatisfied	5	5%
Total	100	100%

INTERPRETATION:

The table shows that, 32% of respondents are Very Satisfied, 34% of them Satisfied, 27% are Neutral, 2% are Dissatisfied and 5% thinks Very dissatisfied through online payment method.

TABLE 10 : FEATURES TO LOOK BEFORE MAKING PAYMENT

SOURCE	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	%
Secure Socket Layer	31	31%
Two factor authentication	31	31%
Verified payment	32	32%
None	6	6%
Total	100	100%

INTERPRETATION:

The table shows that, 31% thinks Secure Socket Layer. 31% thinks Two factor authentication. 32% thinks Verified payment. 6% thinks None.

TABLE 11 : CONFIDENT ABOUT SECURITY MEASURES ON ONLINE PAYMENT

STATEMENT	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	%
Very Confident	31	31%
Confident	38	38%
Somewhat Confident	20	20%
Slightly Confident	8	8%
Not Confident	3	3%
Total	100	100%

INTERPRETATION:

The table shows that out of 100 respondents, 31% of respondents having Very Confident on security about online payment methods, 38% having Confident, 20% having Somewhat Confident, 8% having Slightly Confident and 3% Not Confident on security about online payment methods.

SUGGESTIONS

- Security features before making online payment should be developed.
- Facing of fraud or unauthorized payment should be avoided.
- New payment methods with more security features can be introduced.
- Data privacy can be maintained.
- Payment failures should be noticed and maintained.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, internet marketing offers companies a plethora of chances to interact with clients, reach a worldwide audience, and spur growth in an affordable and quantifiable way. But there are drawbacks as well, such as fierce competition, quickly evolving digital environments, privacy issues, and the requirement for specific skills and resources. Businesses that want to prosper must be flexible, never stop learning, and carefully weigh the advantages and disadvantages of internet marketing. Businesses can overcome these obstacles and succeed in the digital sphere over the long run by using digital tools efficiently, comprehending consumer behaviour, and upholding a continuous brand presence. In the end, taking a deliberate, strategic approach to internet marketing can pay off handsomely, but it takes constant work and a dedication to change the Digital world.

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